

PRODIGEES

Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development

How to interpret this form: This Researcher Declaration is to be read, completed, and signed by the Researcher. By signing this form, you understand and agree to your personal data being processed by IDOS, PRODIGEES and the EU and you understand and agree to produce evidence of your expenditures and activities upon request. This document formalizes your position as a Researcher of PRODIGEES. Please email this document to the PRODIGEES Project Manager, Benjamin Stewart (benjamin.stewart@idos-research.de) and your host supervisor.

Researcher Declaration

Project title: Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development
Project acronym: PRODIGEES
Grant agreement no: 873119
Project dates: January 1, 2020 – June 30, 2025

I will be completing a secondment as part of the PRODIGEES project, and once I have read this declaration and filled in the details required below, I will return it to the PRODIGEES Project Coordinator.

Use of personal data and payroll information for grant funding claims and audits

I understand that as part of my secondment, IDOS, is required to obtain some of my personal information in order to pay a bursary (if applicable). If I am to receive a bursary during the secondment, the project coordinator will ask me to provide bank account details.

I understand that the project may be audited by external auditors/accountants who may request to see evidence relating to my secondments and evidence in relation to personnel costs that I may claim. The evidence required may include, but is not limited to, secondment evidence as noted in this declaration, my identification details and documents, pay information, business-incurred expenses and receipts, employment/student contracts and addendum.

I also understand that any information kept securely on IDOS servers is done so for audit purposes, that it will be retained for the duration of time within which the EU may perform an audit on the project, and that anything shared with external auditors will be done so securely and in strict confidence.

If I have any questions regarding this or object to particular evidence items being shared, I will contact the Project Coordinator.

Secondment related evidence

At the end of the secondment, I understand that I will be reintegrated into my home organisation and will be able to provide evidence of this in the form of a lecture/workshop/presentation to be given at my home organisation, based upon my PRODIGEES research.

I will be able to provide the documents listed below to the Project Coordinator upon request:

1. Proof of my registration/employment with my home institution
2. Proof of travel to the secondment organisation (ex. Flight boarding passes & accommodation information)
3. Proof of arrival at the secondment organisation (ex. Secondment Arrival Letter)
4. Proof of my expenses (ex. Receipts from flights, accommodation, lab and field work, local transport, etc.)
5. Evidence of work during the secondment – (ex. Papers, presentations, meeting notes, time sheets, etc.)
6. Proof that my PRODIGEES research data and publications remain open access.
7. A Secondment Activity Report (a template is provided by the Project Coordinator)

Researcher Declaration

I understand that for external audit purposes, I am required to keep my original passport for 6 years after the end of the project, and will provide this to the project coordinator if requested.

Title	
First Name	
Last Name	
Gender	
Date of Birth	
Nationality	
Status – ESR or ER? (Early Stage Researcher = first 4 years of research career and no PhD / Experienced Researcher = with doctoral degree or 4 years full time equivalent experience)	
Start date of secondment	
End date of secondment	
Sending organisation	
Secondment organisation	
Which countries have you lived in?	
Which Work Package/s are you working on? (WP2: Governance and Society OR WP3: Economy and Environment)	
Email address:	
Are you enrolled in a PhD programme?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
I have been actively engaged in – or linked to – research and/or innovation activities at the sending institution for at least one month (full-time equivalent and continuously) or at least two months (part-time equivalent) immediately prior to the first period of secondment	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
I confirm that I am <i>not</i> being funded by another Marie-Sklodowska-Curie Action during my participation in this secondment	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
My working time commitment during the secondment will be 100% (please note this must be 100%)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

I confirm that I have read this declaration, that the information provided is correct, and that the documents listed will be provided within the requested timeframe.

Date _____

Signature of Researcher _____

